

NCAS Capel Dewi
Atmospheric Observatory
<https://amof.ac.uk/observatory/>

Minutes of the 66th Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory Users' Meeting

which was held online on 26th February 2021.

(This document was finalised on 8th July 2021)

Present:

(BB) Dr Barbara Brooks^{4,6}
(CJW) Dr Chris Walden^{4,5}
(DAH) Dr David Hooper^{1,4,5} Secretary
(EGN) Dr Emily Norton⁴
(GV) Prof Geraint Vaughan^{4,7} Chair
(GAP) Dr Graham Parton^{2,4,5}
(HMAR) Dr Hugo Ricketts^{4,7}
(LD) Mr Les Dean¹

Affiliation:

¹Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory (CDAO)

²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)

⁴National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)

⁵STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁶University of Leeds

⁷University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

AMOF Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility
DW Dave Wareing
H&S Health and Safety
IP Internet Protocol
ISP Internet Service Provider
MST Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar)
PAT Portable Appliance Testing
RWP Radar Wind Profiler
STFC Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply
USO Universal Service Obligation (for broadband)
UTC Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

There were no comments on the minutes of the previous meeting.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had extended the coverage of v4 files for most of the period for which v3 files are available.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH to introduce a mechanism to allow users to access data files that have not yet passed quality control checks and been delivered to the CEDA archives.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not made any progress on this since the previous meeting.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make available the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data in NCAS-approved files through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made some progress with dealing with the LD40 data, which he would report in section 4d.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not made any progress on this since the previous meeting. GAP suggested that the data could be made available using the CEDA comma separated variable format.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not made any progress on this since the previous meeting.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a consistent archive structure for the different versions of MST Radar data products files.

ONGOING

GAP will report on progress made in section 3a.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to arrange for installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton staff, for the latter part of 2019.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this action was on hold owing to Covid-19 restrictions.

ACTION ITEM 64.2.1 DAH and GAP to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar available through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not made any progress on this since the previous meeting.

ACTION ITEM 65.3.1 DAH to make enquires about the possibility of installing a fibre broadband connection to the CDAO.

ONGOING

DAH will report on his progress with this in section 3c.

3. Observatory Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP reported that CEDA had created a new, consistent way of accessing datasets for which naming conventions and directory structures have changed over time. This will exist in parallel with the historical directory structures. Elements of the new directory paths will cover the names of the observation location, the instrument, the deployment, the version of the dataset, and the release type. Storage space has been allocated for the new structures and GAP is in the process of implementing them. The MST Radar dataset is unusual since the availability of the distinct M and ST mode observations does not have a parallel with other instruments.

3b) Electricity - DAH

DAH reported that he had purchased a small Portable Appliance Testing (PAT) instrument, in January 2021, for LD to use at the CDAO. PAT had been due to be carried out by a local electrician in March 2020, but the person responsible was off sick that week. Subsequent Covid-19 restrictions on people visiting the CDAO have meant that this work could not yet be rescheduled. Although LD has extensive experience of carrying out PAT, the STFC Health and Safety (H&S) officer stipulated that he must attend an approved training course in order to be regarded as being competent to carry out the task. Since in-person training has not been appropriate under Covid-19 restrictions, the STFC H&S officer suggested that LD should simply carry out a visual inspection of power cables. DAH had thought that it would not take LD much more time to carry out full PAT and that the outcome would be more useful even if it is not recognised as being valid by STFC.

All Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) sites will be switching electricity provider from British Gas to EDF on 1st April 2021. Consequently LD has been asked to take photographs of the meter readings once a month for the 3 months leading up to 1st April so that the final bills can be confirmed. Since the meter has only been read on an infrequent basis, and most of the bills use estimated readings, this exercise will give a useful indication of the typically monthly consumption at the site.

LD installed a new Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) unit in the workshop room next to the external instrument compound in December 2020. This is intended to reduce the load on the UPS unit supplying equipment within the receiver room. A time will need to be agreed with HMAR for powering down the Lufft ceilometer so that it can be transferred to the new UPS unit.

The existing UPS units switched to battery power in response to input power problems on 4 occasions during the previous 6 months. None of these problems lasted for more than 1 s.

3c) Telecommunications

Owing to the slow broadband connection speeds for the CDAO, DAH has been investigating the possibility of ordering "fibre to the premises on demand", i.e. addressing action item 65.3.1. Details on the Openreach website in July 2020 showed that *The cabinet you're connected to is enabled for fibre. However you're not able to order a service. This might be because you're too far from the cabinet.* Although the existing Internet Service Provider (ISP) is not able to offer this service in the Aberystwyth area, a member of their technical support staff informed DAH that he might be able to make use of the Government's legally-binding Universal Service Obligation (USO). As of March 2020, customers who are unable to get a download speed of at least 10 Mbit/s and an upload speed of 1 Mbit/s are entitled to request an upgraded connection. However, the USO only covers the first £3400 of the cost of installation. The customer is liable for any excess costs, which can amount to tens of thousands of pounds.

DAH has registered his interest through the Openreach website, but cannot take this any further until the service is available for the Capel Dewi area.

In parallel with this, LD has investigated the possibility of establishing a 4G mobile data connection to the CDAO. Since mobile reception at the site is so poor, LD had to wander around with an external antenna attached to a broom handle so that he could identify the best location for it. He eventually (on 16th October 2020) fixed it to the west side of the bungalow. He used a GiffGaff account, which piggybacks on the O2 network, and found that he could get good 4G download speeds. DAH reported that the Draytek router has the capacity to support a mobile connection in addition to the land line one. In principle, it can be configured to switch to the mobile connection only when the land line is down. The main problem would be that the standard mobile packages available through STFC do not give a fixed Internet Protocol (IP) address. This would prevent connections being made to the CDAO network from the outside. BB recommended that DAH should speak to Dan and James at NCAS to find out how they were able to provide fixed IP address mobile connections for remote sites. GV highlighted how important it was to improve the internet connection to the site and so urged DAH to persist with this line of enquiry.

DAH had purchased a new Draytek router and posted this to LD just before the first Covid-19 lockdown began at the end of March 2020. Although DAH had configured the router beforehand, it turns out that he had made one small mistake. This meant that although LD could connect to the internet from within the CDAO network, DAH could not connect to the CDAO network from the outside. Since this would have been a serious limiting factor, LD had instead installed the old Speedtouch router, which DAH had also configured and posted to LD in March 2020. Although this router had initially proved to be reliable, it started to have connection issues in late July 2020. The ISP deliberately dropped the connection speed in an attempt to make the connection more reliable. Although this initially appeared to help, the connection issues became more numerous and more prolonged in September 2020. This led LD to attempt to install the new Draytek router on 29th September 2020. It turns out that the configuration error made by DAH had been simple to correct. The router lost its connection during the early morning of 28th October 2020 and had to be power-cycled by LD later the same day in order for normal operations to be resumed. However, it has maintained its connection ever since. DAH ordered a spare Draytek router in December 2020. He order another one in January 2021 with the intention that it could be used on one of the spare lines.

3d) Miscellaneous

DAH has revised the estimate of the altitude of the base of the MST Radar's antenna array from 50 m above mean sea level to 45 m. The original estimate was made from an Ordnance Survey's 1:50,000 scale Landranger map. However, whilst HMAR was submitting details of the Lufft ceilometer for AERONET registration, he discovered that higher resolution map products can now be accessed online: <https://osmaps.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/52.42431,-4.00520,18>. This shows that the 50 m contour intersects the Capel Dewi road pretty much exactly where the site track meets it. Since this is somewhat above the top of the 4.5 m high Yagi aerials, DAH estimated the base of the antenna array to be 5 m below this. DAH also examined the elevations from the Ordnance Survey's OS Terrain 50 dataset, which he has used to create terrain maps for the Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF) website. The values for the four 50 m by 50 m squares that contain parts of the antenna array are 47.7, 48.3, 48.3, 48.7 m. However, since each of these squares contains land outside of the array, and since it is not clear whether the elevation values represent means or something else, DAH preferred to use the estimate taken from the online map referenced above. DAH was unable to improve on the estimate of 140 m for the base of the 10 m tower at Frongoch since it is somewhat offset from the nearest contour: <https://osmaps.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/52.42356,-4.05399,18>. The actual elevation is likely to be no more than a metre or two below 140 m.

DAH reported that the current Covid-19 restrictions on people visiting the CDAO will remain in place

for the time being. This is primarily for the benefit of LD and Dave Wareing (DW), who would prefer not to have to come into contact with more people than is strictly necessary. Anyone wanting to visit the site must first gain permission from DAH and he will only grant this if LD and DW are happy for him to do so. There are currently national restrictions on people visiting Wales from other parts of the UK.

DAH reported that the fire extinguishers had been tested by a fire safety officer from Aberystwyth University on 23rd February 2021.

4. CDAO Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH reported that LD had cleaned the tipping bucket rain gauge on 7th August 2020. This had required DAH to blank the tip detected during the period 10:50 - 11:00 UTC, which did not represent rain.

DAH noted that 20th January 2021 was one of the wettest days ever recorded at the CDAO. Rain fell with moderate intensity for virtually the whole day, leading to an accumulation of 45.0 mm. A similar accumulation of 45.6 mm for 20th July 2010 had resulted primarily from two periods of heavy rain, each of which had lasted for a few hours. However, the wettest day ever was 8th June 2012, which led to an accumulation of 52.8 mm. This was also from rain falling with moderate intensity for virtually the whole day.

DAH drew attention to the fact that a number of measurements made by the tipping bucket rain gauge over the past two months should be treated with caution. This is a consequence of frequent sub-zero temperatures. For example, the LD40 indicated clear skies for most of the day on 9th January 2021. The single tip detected during the interval 12:00 - 12:10 UTC appears to have been the result of frost melting. On 14th February 2021, the LD40 showed 3 periods of precipitation between 09:30 and 14:10 UTC. The precipitation is assumed to have fallen as snow that subsequently melted slowly, since no tips were registered until 14:20 UTC and two more were registered over the next hour and a half. The situation on 31st December 2020 is more complicated. The first measurement made by tipping bucket rain gauge during the interval 11:30 - 11:40 UTC appears to be the result of snow melting. However, subsequent tips are likely to represent actual rain. DAH has recorded details of these issues in the instrument log. However, he has allowed the suspect values to be available in the NASA Ames data files since the existing format does not allow reliability flags to be included. This issue can be addressed when the data are made available in netCDF format files. GV advised DAH to implement a simple flagging system since trying to establish exactly what was going on during cold conditions could be very time consuming.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

DAH reported that since Covid-19 restrictions had prevented him from visiting the CDAO, the problem with erroneous wind directions was still occurring. The current NASA Ames files record wind as northward and eastward components. Since both values are affected by errors in the direction, there is no way of indicating that just the direction is unreliable. The problem can only be overcome by storing the data as speed and direction. DAH will do this when he moves to storing the data in netCDF format.

There had been a problem with the logger occasionally dropping its 3G data connection, which required the modem to be power-cycled for the connection to be re-established. In order to avoid this problem, on 28th August 2020 LD installed a timer unit to switch off the 12 V supply to the modem for 5 minutes at 14:30 UTC each day. There have been no subsequent problems with lost connections.

Whilst he was looking for AMOF supported publications, DAH came across a paper in Weather by David Smart entitled "*Short report: a damaging downslope wind storm in western Wales on 1-2 March*

2018" - <https://doi.org/10.1002/wea.3615>. The paper had not used data from Frongoch, but had stated, "*Mean winds and gusts recorded at the Natural Environment Research Council facilities outside Aberystwyth were not notable, although some damage was reported in the town itself.*" DAH had contacted the author with details of the CDAO data that might be relevant to this study. The author had only been aware of the MST Radar data and agreed that the surface wind speeds recorded at Frongoch (gust speeds had peaked at 30 m/s) were indeed notable. He asked DAH to write a follow-up article for Weather to correct the record. DAH will need to create a climatology of sustained and gust wind speeds in order to put this event in context. As a preliminary exercise, he recreated the standard data plots available through CEDA for the period between December 2001 and April 2015. The older style plots only showed speeds up to 20 m/s rather than the 35 m/s used for the newer style. As a result of looking through the plots for the whole dataset, DAH has identified a number of issues.

Problems establishing a daily dial-up modem connection to the Frongoch logger were relatively common during the early 2000s. As long as the connection could be established on the following day, no raw data were lost. However, since the NASA Ames files were generated automatically on a daily basis, some contain missing datum values for times that were subsequently covered by the following day's download of raw data. If the connection problem persisted for more than two and a half days, the oldest raw data would be overwritten within the logger. Under such circumstances, DAH's NASA Ames file creation software appropriately inserted missing datum values for the lost periods. However, there were occasional periods, such as, between 14th and 22nd September 2009, when the logger was not able to record raw data from the sensors. The NASA Ames files inappropriately contain zero values for speed and direction when they should contain missing datum values. DAH has made a log of such periods and these can be dealt with when he releases an updated version of the dataset.

DAH identified a more subtle issue arising from his use of vector averaging (i.e. applied to eastward and northward components) for calculating the mean wind vector. He had always considered this to be more appropriate than scalar averaging (i.e. applied to speed and direction). Although differences between the two methods are typically small, the speed derived by vector averaging can be much smaller than that derived by scalar averaging when the direction undergoes large changes during the averaging period. This can occur either because there is a step change in the sustained wind direction, e.g. as seen just before 16:00 UTC on 1st March 2015, or because the wind direction shows large fluctuations over a more prolonged period, e.g. as seen between 07:30 and 14:00 UTC on 21st April 2013. DAH first identified this issue by noticing that the vector averaged speed dropped below the minimum gust speed during such periods. He had contacted Jeremy Price to ask what whether he had seen anything similar and was surprised to hear that Jeremy preferred to use scalar averaging. DAH now considers scalar averaging to give a more representative indication of the strength of the wind than vector averaging and will henceforth use this for the standard plots.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

DAH reported that he had ceased to see rogue characters in the logs of raw data from this instrument. GV suggested that DAH should prioritise making the data from this instrument publicly available.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

The raw data messages produced by the LD40 use a mixture of text and binary encodings. Since DAH has experience of writing python software for handling this, he has been helping Judith Jeffrey and CJW to replace their existing Matlab code for handling the "format 5" raw data logs produced for the disdrometers operated by the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory. The format was designed over 25 years ago, partly with minimising the stored data volume in mind, but had never been documented. DAH was responsible for writing the lowest-level routines for interpreting the data logs. He did this using python 3 and will adapt what he has learnt so that his routines for handling LD40 raw data logs are also written in python 3.

4e) Lufft Ceilometer

HMAR reported that the ceilometer was working well. Its window needs regular cleaning, which has been carried out by LD and DW since March 2020. HMAR would like to install a Raspberry Pi computer on the CDAO network so that he can carry out processing tasks locally. GAP pointed out that it might be better to carry out processing tasks on the JASMIN computing system rather than locally.

HMAR reported that the new sun photometer had been installed near the mobile lab at the CDAO on 12th January 2021. It is able to make use of light from the moon as well as from the sun. This allowed its performance to be evaluated despite the relative lack of sunlight during the mid-winter period. The unit will be bookable for AMOF-supported field campaigns, but will be operated at the CDAO when not otherwise required. Data are currently being sent to AERONET every 5 minutes. The instrument will need to be occasionally sent away for calibration. CJW explained that the data from the Chilbolton sun photometer are subsequently picked up by a number of users through AERONET. It was only possible to get an idea of how the data are used if an appropriate acknowledgment or citation is included in papers.

In response to BB's question about the new micropulse lidar, HMAR explained that he would set it up at the air quality supersite in Manchester, but it might come down to the CDAO at a later date. GV added that if it is really capable of observing up to 15 km, it would add most value if it were operated at the CDAO. Observations would only be required to the lower altitudes to be of use for air quality studies.

4f) Sky Cameras

DAH had nothing to report on this instrument.

4g) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH had nothing to report on this instrument.

4h) MST Radar

Until September 2020, text-based wind-profile data files were converted to BUFR format locally before being sent to E-PROFILE. It turns out that the CDAO was the only provider still using this old method. The preferred method is now to submit text-based files, which can be converted to other formats at the E-PROFILE hub. DAH had to make some small changes to the format of the text-based files for the new system and began to send these in parallel with the BUFR messages on 18th August 2020. Once E-PROFILE were happy that the new files were being accepted by their hub, a switch over from the BUFR files for operational purposes was made on 2nd September 2020. This caused a problem almost immediately with the appearance of clearly-unreliable winds at altitudes of around 13 km. DAH quickly established that these winds had been flagged as being unreliable in the files that he had submitted, but the E-PROFILE system was not recognising these flags. The solution was to simply omit these data points from the text-based file.

As a consequence of the changes made to the text-based files, plots of the latest data from the E-PROFILE feed on the supplementary website, <http://www.mstrf.eclipse.co.uk/>, which are labeled as "*MST Radar - ST mode - 30 minute averaged 300 m resolution*", are not currently available. DAH will have to make modifications to his scripts to handle the new file format.

The standard data files for 12th September and 24th December 2020 contained wind speeds that were unrealistically fast within limited time-altitude regions. The files for 29th July, 3rd August, and 16th August 2020 were affected by "Sporadic E" type contamination within limited time regions but across a range of altitudes. These data files have been released to the archive labeled as containing suspect data. A larger number of files suffered from a raised noise floor, which reduced the useful altitude coverage, but which did not lead to contamination of the data products. This problem began late on the 20th January 2021, i.e. the day mentioned in section 4a when there had been an accumulation of 45.0 mm of rain. It had persisted, albeit in a time varying way, until around 13th February 2021. The assumption

is that was a consequence of the antenna array remaining water-logged. GV asked if anything could be done to prevent the problem. LD pointed out that the cables had been buried for 30 years and so it would not be practical to try to dig them up.

5. Guest Instrument Report

EGN reported she had finished releasing data from the Radar Wind Profiler (RWP) in files that are compliant with the original version of the NCAS data standard. She will switch to using the latest version of the standard for ongoing data.

Some elements of the RWP's hardware, including the PCA computer and the processing/control boards, were upgraded in November 2020. Owing to a tightening of Covid-19 restrictions, EGN had been unable to visit the CDAO and so DW had installed the new units. Initially, all of the spectra looked as though they were from vertical beam observations. Then the RWP stopped working on 23rd November, with several fault lights indicating problems on the processing board. Although the system looked to be in better health on 26th November, once again all of the data looked as though they related to vertical beam observations. DW discovered that a power supply unit had failed, apparently as a result of two cables being installed the wrong way round. This had caused one of the chips to fail, although LD was able to supply a replacement from his collection. Once the RWP was back in operation, the wind directions looked wrong. On 16th December, it was discovered that the I and Q channels had accidentally be swapped over (probably by the manufacturer). The system is now capable of making observations up to higher altitudes than previously, 8 km rather than 6 km, which will be useful for carrying out comparisons with wind data from the MST Radar. Useful observations during storm Bella on 26th/27th December 2020 only reached up to 6 km. EGN experimented with different settings of the consensus averaging algorithm in order to maximise the useful coverage. There are still some issues arising from the upgrade, but it appears to have improved performance. The data files are much bigger than they used to be and now amount to around 3 GBytes per day.

GAP asked if details of the upgrade could be provided to put on the CEDA catalogue page. EGN thought that the instrument was essentially the same as previously and so there was no need to regard it as a new instrument.

GV reported that his paper on Raman lidar observations of ash from volcano Raikoke had recently been accepted for publication. The lidar has not made many observations recently and DW will need to carry out alignment work. Although the Elight lidar is capable of operations, it has experienced a number of problems. DW has not had time to look at these since he has been spending most of his time dealing with the RWP and sun photometer.

DAH reported that the Met Office no longer require their GPS receiver at the CDAO for operational purposes and so it can be switched off.

6. Any Other Business

The provisional date for the next meeting was set for mid July 2021.